

The Role of Work Attitude in Mediating the Influence of Leadership Style and Work Environment on Employee Performance of the Food and Beverage Companies in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: The Food and Beverage industry plays a strategic role in the country's economic growth. Understanding the factors that influence the long-term success of F&B businesses is important and interesting. This study aims to analyze the role of work attitudes as a mediating variable in the influence of leadership style and work environment on employee performance in F&B companies in Indonesia. A sample of 182 operational employees was taken using convenience sampling techniques. A quantitative approach with SEM PLS analysis was used to test the influence of variables in the study. The results showed that the work environment did not have a direct influence on employee performance, but there was a full mediating role of work attitudes in influencing employee performance. This study also concluded that leadership style directly influenced work attitudes and employee performance, and the work environment directly influenced work attitudes. The originality of this study emphasized the importance of work attitudes related to initiatives to improve better work processes and the importance of leadership that tends to be autocratic where leaders provide clear directions to complete work well which will have an impact on positive work attitudes and good performance.

KEYWORDS: Leadership Style, Work Environment, Work Attitude, Employee Performance, Food and Beverage Industry.

INTRODUCTION

The food and beverage industry is a strategic sector that significantly contributes to Indonesia's national economic growth. According to data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), Indonesia's economic growth in the fourth quarter of 2025 is projected to reach 5.11% year-on-year, with the processing industry being the main contributor to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (BPS, 2026). Within this sector, the food and beverage subsector plays a key role in driving growth, driven by increased domestic and export demand, as well as support from fiscal stimulus and increased public mobility to meet needs and lifestyle preferences. Furthermore, technological advances, the expansion of the e-commerce market, and product diversification have strengthened the competitiveness of the food and beverage industry, with the rise in online food and beverage orders. However, despite this rapid growth, the food and beverage industry also faces challenges in innovation and service quality, which require skilled human resource management. Human resources are currently required to be learners with a positive attitude, namely individuals who are willing to learn, take initiative with enthusiasm so that their human potential and behavior can develop optimally to provide optimal contributions in the work environment (Sumiarti & Purbasari, 2019).

The idea that competition for the future is about gaining a greater share of opportunities than just market share, is of interest to company management (Karmilati & Purbasari, 2012). Paying attention to employee performance issues is the responsibility of managerial positions in companies. The company's ability to understand the factors that determine employee performance is a requirement that must be addressed wisely. Employee performance is a crucial factor in determining an organization's success in achieving its strategic goals. Employee performance is defined as someone who carries out their work efficiently and effectively to achieve goals by providing the best possible work methods (Purbasari & Septian, 2017). Performance is a manifestation of an individual's ability to produce work output in accordance with targets, standards, and responsibilities assigned to them. Performance is also defined as the results of individual behavior that are relevant to organizational goals and can be measured based on their effectiveness and efficiency (Judge, 2017). Performance at a conceptual level, is defined as a set of actions and behaviors carried out by individuals that contribute to the achievement of organizational goals; performance includes what workers do in the workplace and the results obtained from those actions (Campbell et al., 1990). Employee performance is recognized as a multidimensional construct reflecting the effectiveness, efficiency, accuracy, and quality of individual contributions. Employee performance refers not only to what is accomplished, but also to how an individual carries out their work,

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including perseverance, thoroughness, commitment, and behaviors that support smooth operations (Podsakoff et al., 2009). High-performing employees typically have a good understanding of their tasks, are able to work consistently, produce output according to standards, and are able to adapt to dynamic job demands. The quality of work results and the accuracy of task completion are strong indicators of individual performance in various industrial sectors (Viswesvaran & Ones, 2000). Various studies have shown that employee performance is influenced by internal factors such as work attitude, as well as external factors such as leadership style and the work environment (Ridwan et al., 2023);(Cabrera & Estacio, 2022).

A successful leader is one who understands how to use the right leadership style. Leadership involves how a leader behaves toward subordinates. Leadership is a social process that enables individuals to work together to achieve results that would not be possible if working alone (Drath et al., 2008). Leadership style is defined as the way a leader influences, directs, and motivates subordinates. Leadership style is also defined as a leader's attitudes and behaviors, which are the result of a complex interaction between the individual's way of thinking and feeling as a leader (Purbasari & Septian, 2017). In situational theory, leadership styles can vary depending on the situation, the maturity level of subordinates, the task, and the context, meaning there is no single best style for all conditions (Supatmin et al., 2021). Effective leaders not only provide direction but are also able to create supportive interpersonal relationships and encourage employees to actively participate in achieving organizational goals. Good leadership can foster a culture of open communication, improve work morale, and reduce conflict, thereby encouraging employees to actively participate, show initiative, and work creatively in completing work demands (Imran et al., 2025); (Yan et al., 2021). Conversely, poor or authoritarian leadership can decrease motivation, create psychological distance, and inhibit participation, ultimately negatively impacting employee performance (Zhao & Sheng, 2019).

Improving employee performance depends not only on leadership style but also on the organization's ability to provide a supportive work environment. The work environment can be defined as the environment in which employees work, encompassing all conditions, situations, and elements surrounding individuals that can influence how they think, behave, and carry out daily activities. The work environment is also understood as the overall conditions of the workplace, the work community environment, and social or organizational support that influence employee performance (Zhenjing et al., 2022). A conducive work environment encompasses physical conditions such as a comfortable workspace, lighting, and security, as well as psychological conditions such as relationships between coworkers, social support, and a positive communication climate. A good work environment increases productivity and fosters a positive work attitude, ultimately improving employee performance (Chandrasekar, 2011). Employee perceptions of a comfortable and supportive work environment have a direct relationship with improved performance (Zhenjing et al., 2022).

However, various studies have shown varying and even contradictory results. Leadership style has a significant influence on employee performance (Arifuddin et al., 2023), while other studies indicate that this influence is insignificant or only indirect (Arifin, 2020); (Rozi et al., 2022). Similarly, research findings on the influence of the work environment on employee performance are also inconsistent. Some studies find a positive relationship between the work environment and employee performance (Suwandana, 2025); (Zhenjing et al., 2022). While other studies show no direct effect (Rachmania et al., 2025). These differing results indicate a research gap that requires further investigation, particularly regarding the role of mediating variables such as work attitude.

Employee attitudes determine how behavior, tasks, and responsibilities are carried out; conversely, employee behavior related to tasks and responsibilities will reflect work attitudes. Attitude is an internal tendency within an individual formed from a combination of beliefs, feelings, experiences, and personal assessments of a particular object, situation, or condition. This is reinforced by research that states, "attitudes are beliefs and opinions that support or inhibit behavior" (Blanchard, 2010). Attitudes involve a person's evaluation of issues related to perceived and observed objects or events, and position the person to engage in certain behaviors (Purbasari & Karmilati, 2018). Work attitudes vary in intensity, depending on an individual's likes and dislikes of any behavior related to the job itself (Quines & Nino, 2023). Work attitudes are also defined as a psychological factor that reflects an employee's level of commitment, responsibility, and satisfaction with their work. Work attitudes serve as an important mediator between managerial factors (such as leadership style and work environment) and performance outcomes. A positive work attitude can strengthen the relationship between effective leadership and a work environment that supports employee performance. A positive work attitude has also been shown to be an important psychological factor that encourages employee initiative in the workplace. Initiatives are more likely to emerge when employees have positive work attitudes such as self-confidence, involvement, and a strong goal orientation, which influence good employee performance (Frese & Fay, 2001). On the other hand, negative work attitudes can lead to decreased employee performance (Quines & Nino, 2023).

The interrelationships between these variables suggest a causal relationship that is not simple. A positive leadership style builds trust and emotional support in employees, which then improves their work attitudes. When employees feel valued, empowered, and listened to, they develop more positive work attitudes, leading to improved performance. Similarly, a conducive work environment creates physical and psychological comfort that allows employees to work with focus, feel safe, and develop positive

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affect toward their work, which in turn improves work attitudes and performance. Thus, it is understandable that the effects of leadership and the work environment on performance are often indirect and mediated by work attitudes. This aligns with Social Exchange Theory, which suggests that employees tend to respond positively with good work attitudes and high performance when they feel treated fairly, supported, and appreciated by their leaders and the organization (Blau, 2017).

Based on previous research, there are still discrepancies in the results and emerging ideas that have prompted the idea of conducting research on the influence of leadership style and the work environment on employee performance as mediated by work attitudes in companies in the Indonesian food and beverage industry. It is hoped that this research aims to analyze the influence of leadership style and work environment on employee performance with work attitude as a mediating variable in the F&B industry in Indonesia.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A) Leadership Style on Employee Performance

Leadership style is a crucial element in organizational success because it determines how a leader influences, motivates, and directs employees to achieve company goals. Leadership style is a behavioral pattern used by a leader to organize, guide, and influence subordinates to work effectively (Judge, 2017). Leadership styles are attitudes and behaviors of leader these in turn are the outcome of complex interactions between the way individuals think and feel as a leader (Purbasari & Septian, 2017); (Khan, 2016). Effective leadership can build trust, create open communication, and increase work morale, which ultimately has a positive impact on employee performance. Leaders who encourage open communication and involve employees in decision-making can increase a sense of ownership in their work and improve performance outcomes (Arifuddin et al., 2023). However, other studies have shown different results. Leadership style does not always have a direct impact on performance, but rather influences it through psychological factors such as work attitude (Arifin, 2020).

Leaders must be able to provide clear direction, emotional support, and ongoing motivation to enable employees to maintain optimal performance, especially when facing high work pressure and customer demands (Rozi et al., 2022). Leaders who are able to provide direction, support, and motivation will help employees maintain optimal performance amidst the dynamics of a competitive industry. This finding is supported by research that suggests that responsive and adaptive leaders can increase employee engagement in the work process, resulting in significant performance improvements, which in turn significantly improve performance (Olasehinde, 2024). Overall, leadership style plays a crucial role in improving employee performance, both directly and through psychological mechanisms such as work attitudes. Therefore, it can be affirmed that an effective leadership style positively influences employee performance, leading to the following hypothesis:

H1: Leadership style influences employee performance.

B) Work Environment on Employee Performance

The work environment is the overall physical, social, and psychological conditions within the workplace that can influence employee behavior and work outcomes. A good work environment is characterized by safe and comfortable physical conditions and harmonious social relationships among employees (Athirah et al., 2019). A positive work environment improves performance by increasing motivation and reducing work stress (Zhenjing et al., 2022). Therefore, a comfortable work environment with low stress levels will improve employee performance.

The workplace environment refers to the relationship between work, the workplace, and work tools, where the workplace is an integral part of the work itself (Purbasari & Septian, 2017). A good work environment creates an environment where people enjoy what they do, feel a sense of purpose, take pride in what they do, and can reach their potential (Bushiri & Peter, 2014). Therefore, it can be explained that comfortable, safe, and physically and psychologically supportive working conditions support employees in carrying out their daily work activities. A comfortable workplace not only impacts employee well-being but can also reduce work error rates and increase the efficiency and effectiveness of task execution (Suwandana, 2025). A supportive work environment, both physically and socially, is a crucial factor for optimal work performance, which impacts employee performance. Based on the explanation above, the work environment has a positive effect on employee performance, thus the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H2: The work environment influences employee performance.

C) Leadership Style towards Work Attitude

Work attitude reflects an individual's overall evaluation of their job, encompassing emotional, cognitive, and behavioral aspects. Work attitude reflects an employee's level of engagement, satisfaction, and commitment to their job and organization (Judge, 2017). A positive work attitude encourages employees to work harder, be more responsible, and be results-oriented. Leadership style is a key factor shaping employee work attitudes (Quines & Nino, 2023). Leaders who provide support, recognition, and fairness foster positive attitudes, while an authoritarian leadership style or an uncomfortable work environment can dampen

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morale. A supportive leadership style, providing clear direction, rewards, and open discussion can foster positive work attitudes because employees feel valued and involved in organizational processes. This aligns with findings confirming that positive psychological factors such as personal initiative, triggered by positive treatment from leaders, are closely related to the emergence of more constructive work attitudes and influence work performance (Luthans et al., 2007). Overall, leadership style plays a significant role in improving work attitudes, thus confirming that leadership style has a positive effect on work attitudes, as hypothesized as follows:

H3: Leadership style influences work attitudes.

D) Work Environment on Work Attitude

Work attitude is an employee's evaluative reflection of their work and work environment, reflected through their experiences interacting with work conditions, both physical and psychosocial. A positive work attitude is an important indicator of organizational sustainability because it is linked to constructive work behavior (Saari & Judge, 2004). The work environment plays a strategic role in shaping work attitudes because it serves as the primary context in which employees interact, adapt, and evaluate their work. The work environment relates not only to the technical aspects of the job but also encompasses employees' experiences of the physical and social conditions in the workplace. One factor, particularly lighting quality, influences comfort and concentration, and thus employees' psychological attitudes toward their work (Kort & Veitch, 2014). When the work environment is perceived positively, employees tend to develop optimal work attitudes (Briner, 2000). Based on the explanation above, it can be confirmed that the work environment has a positive effect on work attitudes, leading to the following hypothesis:

H4: The work environment influences work attitudes.

E) Work Attitude towards Employee Performance

Work attitude is a psychological factor that plays a crucial role in determining how an employee behaves and performs. A positive work attitude reflects satisfaction, commitment, and involvement with work, which encourages improved performance and accountability for work outcomes (Judge, 2017). Work attitude significantly impacts employee performance, particularly when employees feel valued and supported by their superiors (Quines & Nino, 2023). Work attitude serves as a mediating variable between managerial factors and performance outcomes (Nugroho, & Wahjoedi, 2023). Employee initiative can be used as an important indicator in shaping work attitudes. This is reinforced by findings confirming that personal initiative plays a significant role in influencing employee performance (Gamboa et al., 2009). This study indicates that the higher an employee's personal initiative, the higher their work performance, thus initiative can be considered a key indicator of work attitude. Initiative reflects an employee's tendency to be proactive, independent, and have control over their work, ultimately leading to more positive evaluations of their work and organizational environment.

These findings align with research emphasizing that work attitudes are influenced not only by perceptions of the work environment and leadership style, but also by proactive behaviors such as involvement and initiative in carrying out tasks (Cabrera & Estacio, 2022). The study explains that employees who demonstrate high levels of initiative tend to have more positive work attitudes because they feel more responsible, empowered, and connected to organizational goals. Work attitudes shaped by proactive behaviors such as initiative have a direct impact on improved employee performance, particularly because they are better prepared to face work demands and demonstrate a stronger commitment to completing tasks. Thus, it can be affirmed that work attitudes positively influence employee performance, leading to the following hypothesis:

H5: Work attitudes influence employee performance.

F) The Mediating Role of Work Attitudes

Based on Social Exchange Theory, the relationship between employees and the organization is based on the principle of reciprocity (Blau, 2017). When leaders provide support, appreciation, and a positive work environment, employees will reciprocate with positive attitudes, such as work initiatives and improved performance. Other research also demonstrates that a positive work environment improves performance, especially when employees develop a more optimistic, motivated, and emotionally engaged work attitude (Bakker et al., 2007). Previous research indicates that work attitude plays a mediating role between managerial factors (leadership style and work environment) and employee performance (Quines & Nino, 2023). When employees feel treated fairly and comfortably in the work environment, they develop positive attitudes that are reflected in productive work behavior. Therefore, this study assumes that work attitude is a mediating variable between leadership style and work environment on employee performance in the food and beverage industry, as formulated with the following hypotheses:

H6: Work attitude mediates the effect of leadership style on employee performance.

H7: Work attitude mediates the effect of work environment on employee performance

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METHOD

The population of this study included all operational employees who interact directly with daily work processes at food and beverage companies in Indonesia. Respondents worked in operational roles such as production, service, or cashiering, which are directly affected by their superiors' leadership styles, the physical work environment, and daily performance demands. The population is infinite, with an unknown number of employees due to the wide distribution of food and beverage companies across Indonesia. This study obtained a sample of 182 employees selected using a non-probability sampling technique based on ease of access by convenience sampling. The majority of respondents were in the productive age range, with a predominance of high school and college graduates. The proportion of male and female respondents was relatively balanced. Most respondents had worked between one and five years, reflecting the dynamics of the F&B industry, which is known for its high turnover rate but still relies on a young, adaptable workforce. The researcher collected data directly with the help of online media when distributing questionnaires. This study uses a variable measurement instrument with a 5-point Likert scale, namely strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, and strongly agree with the following question items.

Table 1. Construct Measurement

	Item Statements
Leadership Style	My boss often reminds me to do the work quickly and save time.
Work Environment	The lighting in my workplace is adequate to support work productivity. The flow of information between people who are important to my work runs smoothly and effectively.
Work Attitude	I have the initiative to improve work processes.
Employee Performance	My overall work ability is good. I am able to achieve work goals well.

Source: PLS processing results

Data analysis was conducted using variance-based Structural Equation Model (SEM) techniques with the Smart PLS software because this method is suitable for research models with reflective items and causal relationships between latent variables. Overall, this research method provides a strong foundation for analysing the relationship between leadership style, work environment, and work attitudes as mediating in influencing employee performance in the food and beverage companies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research results explained that the characteristics of the 182 respondents who participated in this study were predominantly female (56.0%) with an age range of 18–28 years (77.5%), based on the highest education level of high school or equivalent (50.5%) and dominated by employee with a work period of 1–5 years (72.0%), respondents with contract and part-time status by working hours of 6–8 hours per day (56.6%), and respondents who were permanent employees with a 40-hour work week (52.2%).

In evaluating the measurement model or outer model with the convergent validity test are assessed using factor loadings and AVE Score. An indicator is considered to meet the convergent validity criteria if it has a correlation value of ≥ 0.70 (Hair et al., 2017). The output factor loading values in this test show that all statements for the variables employee performance, leadership style, work attitude, and work environment have loading factor values ≥ 0.70 , thus they are all considered valid. Any items that do not meet this requirement must be discarded.

Table 2. Outer Loading (Loading Factor)

Code	Employee Performance	Leadership Style	Work Attitude	Work Environment
EP1	0.864			
EP4	0.720			
LS4		0.721		
WA7			0.777	
WE1				0.782
WE8				0.787

Source: SmartPLS 4

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The AVE (Average Variance Extracted) results were >0.50 for all constructs, namely EP (0.663), LS (0.634), WA (0.644), and WE (0.638). This indicates that the measurement model meets the assumption of convergent validity.

Table 3. Average Variance Extracted

Construct	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Employee Performance	0.663
Leadership Style	0.634
Work Attitude	0.644
Work Environment	0.638

Source: SmartPLS 4

Discriminant validity represents the extent to which a construct is empirically distinct from other constructs. The method used to assess the existence of discriminant validity is Fornell Larcker (Henseler et al., 2016). The results of discriminant validity (Fornell Larcker) are presented in the following table.

Table 4. Fornell Larcker

Construct	Employee Performance	Leadership Style	Work Attitude	Work Environment
Employee Performance	0.911			
Leadership Style	0.411	1.000		
Work Attitude	0.550	0.624	1.000	
Work Environment	0.586	0.469	0.595	0.901

Source: SmartPLS 4

The model is proven to meet the Fornel and Larcker criteria (correlation of employee performance construct (0.911) > correlation of employee performance and leadership style construct (0.411), employee performance and work attitude (0.550), employee performance and work environment (0.586)), (correlation of leadership style construct (1.000) > correlation of leadership style and employee performance construct (0.411), leadership style and work attitude (0.624), leadership style and work environment (0.469)), (correlation of work attitude construct (1.000) > correlation of work attitude and employee performance construct (0.550), work attitude and leadership style (0.624), work attitude and work environment (0.595)), and (correlation of work environment construct (0.901) > correlation of work environment and employee performance construct (0.586), work environment and leadership style (0.469), work environment and work attitude (0.595)). This indicates that the model meets the assumption of good discriminant validity at the good test criteria level.

Table 5. HTMT

Construct	Employee Performance	Leadership Style	Work Attitude	Work Environment
Employee Performance				
Leadership Style	0.462			
Work Attitude	0.617	0.624		
Work Environment	0.744	0.530	0.676	

Source: SmartPLS 4

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Table 5 shows that the HTMT correlation values between constructs, namely between employee performance and leadership style (0.462), employee performance and work attitude (0.617), employee performance and work environment (0.744), work attitude and leadership style (0.624), work environment and leadership style (0.530), and work environment and work attitude (0.676), are all below the limit of 0.90 ($HTMT < 0.90$). Thus, the measurement model constructed has met the assumption of discriminant validity and is in the category of good testing criteria.

Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability values (Table 6) for measuring construct reliability must be above 0.70, which is considered acceptable, indicating a high level of reliability (Hair et al., 2021). The measurement model constructed consistently and reliably reflects each item, with CA and CR values for the EP, LS, WA, and WE constructs > 0.70 , as shown in the table below.

Table 6. Construct Validity and Reliability

Construct	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability
Employee Performance	0.871	0.875
Leadership Style	0.856	0.864
Work Attitude	0.889	0.890
Work Environment	0.886	0.889

Source: SmartPLS 4

Table 7. VIF

Construct	Employee Performance	Leadership Style	Work Attitude	Work Environment
Employee Performance				
Leadership Style	1.677		1.281	
Work Attitude	2.025			
Work Environment	1.585		1.281	

Source: SmartPLS 4

Based on results of VIF (Table 7) above, all construct correlations, including between leadership style and employee performance, work attitude and employee performance, work environment and employee performance, leadership style and work attitude, and work environment and work attitude, have met the criteria for good testing because they are below 5 (Hair et al., 2014). This indicates that the model built does not experience multicollinearity problems.

Table 8. R-square Value

Construct	R-square
Employee Performance	0.800
Work Attitude	0.750

Source: SmartPLS 4

Based on the R-Square value (Table 8) for the employee performance variable is 0.800, indicating that 80% of the variation in employee performance can be explained by leadership style, work environment, and work attitude. Meanwhile, the remaining 20% is influenced by other factors outside the studied model. Furthermore, the R-Square value of 0.750 for the work attitude variable indicates that 75% of the variation in work attitude can be explained by leadership style and work environment, while the remaining 25% is influenced by external factors.

Based on the Q^2 test results (Table 9), the Q^2 value was greater than 0 ($Q^2 > 0$). This means that the observation values generated by the model, including its parameter estimates, have good predictive relevance. The model is able to explain the information contained in the research, so the model is acceptable, feasible for development, and meets good testing criteria due to its relevant predictive ability.

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Table 9. Prediction Relevance (Q2)

Construct	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)
Employee Performance	0.397
Leadership Style	0.421
Work Attitude	0.490
Work Environment	0.473

Source: SmartPLS 4

This indicates that the items used successfully measure the correlation between the indicator scores and their constructs, thus supporting the construct validity of the measurement model.

Figures 1. Outer Model Test Result

Source: SmartPLS

Table 10. Path Coefficients Results

Construct	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Leadership Style -> Employee Performance	0.273	0.269	0.079	3.468	0.001
Leadership Style -> Work Attitude	0.396	0.397	0.063	6.248	0.000
Work Attitude -> Employee Performance	0.533	0.533	0.075	7.132	0.000
Work Environment -> Employee Performance	0.136	0.141	0.094	1.447	0.148
Work Environment -> Work Attitude	0.507	0.507	0.068	7.446	0.000

Source: SmartPLS 4

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The results of this study (figures 1 and table 10) show that leadership style has an influence on employee performance with a coefficient value of 0.273, T statistic 3.468 (>1.96), and P value 0.001 (<0.05), leadership style has an influence on work attitude with a coefficient value of 0.396, T statistic 6.248 (>1.96), and P value 0.000 (<0.05), and affects employee performance with a coefficient value of 0.533, T statistic 7.132 (>1.96), and P value 0.000 (<0.05). Work environment has no influence on employee performance with a coefficient value of 0.136, T statistic 1.447 (<1.96), and P value 0.148 (>0.05). However, the work environment has an influence on work attitude with a coefficient value of 0.507, T statistic 7.446 (>1.96), and P value 0.000 (<0.05).

Table 11. Path Coefficients Results

Construct	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Leadership Style -> Work Attitude -> Employee Performance	0.211	0.211	0.041	5.094	0.000
Work Environment -> Work Attitude -> Employee Performance	0.270	0.271	0.058	4.670	0.000

Source: SmartPLS 4

The mediation effect indicates the role of a variable as a mediator between two or more variables in the model. The analysis results in table 11 show that work attitude has a partial mediating role in the influence of leadership style on employee performance through work attitude, with a coefficient value of 0.211, T statistic 5.094 (>1.96), and P value 0.000 (<0.05). This means that leadership style can play a role in increasing positive work attitudes, which in turn contribute to employee performance and impact on better employee work results. Work attitude has a full mediating role on employee performance with a coefficient value (influence) of 0.270, T statistic 4.670 (>1.96), and P value 0.000 (<0.05). This means that a good work environment will create a positive work attitude so that good employee performance is achieved, indicated by the achievement of expected employee work results.

Table 12. Effect Size (f2)

Construct	Employee Performance	Leadership Style	Work Attitude	Work Environment
Employee Performance				
Leadership Style	0.094		0.187	
Work Attitude	0.355			
Work Environment	0.021		0.308	

Source: SmartPLS 4

The results in table 12 show that the influence or effect between leadership style and employee performance (0.094 >0.02) is small. The relationship or effect between leadership style and work attitude (0.187 >0.15) is moderate. The relationship or effect between work attitude and employee performance (0.355 >0.35) is strong. The relationship or effect between work environment and employee performance (0.021 >0.02) is small, and the relationship or effect between work environment and work attitude (0.308 >0.15) is moderate.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

This study concludes that work attitude influences employee performance and that positive employee work attitude plays a remarkable role as a fully mediating factor in the work environment's impact on employee performance and partially mediating the influence of leadership style on employee performance in companies in the food and beverage (F&B) industry in Indonesia. The results of this study also indicate that leadership style has a direct influence on employee performance and work attitude. The work environment was not proven to have a direct effect on employee performance, but it did have a direct influence on work attitude. These findings confirm that work attitude is a key psychological factor in employees, bridging the influence of the work environment on employee performance, acting as a full mediator in companies in the food and beverage sector, which operate in a

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dynamic work environment with high task pressure and operational demands. Work attitude also has implications for the relationship between leadership style and employee performance, explaining its role as a partially mediating factor.

The originality of this study's findings is demonstrated by the key elements that reflect the dimensions of each variable in the research model and serve as an argumentative basis for recommendations that can be provided to company management in the Indonesian food and beverage industry. Emphasizing a leadership style oriented toward work effectiveness, particularly through providing clear direction and consistently reminding employees about the speed and efficiency of task completion, will impact results or performance and foster better work attitudes. Leadership that actively reminds employees to work on time and conserve resources has been proven to foster work attitudes that foster employee initiative in completing tasks, ultimately positively impacting the performance of operational employees. Furthermore, companies need to create a work environment that supports performance by providing adequate physical conditions, particularly adequate lighting in the work area, and ensuring a smooth flow of information between employees who play a crucial role in task execution. This research is also expected to provide an empirical contribution to the advancement of management science, particularly in the field of behavioral science and human resource management, it emphasize the important role of work attitudes as a mediating variable in explaining how leadership style and the work environment influence employee performance.

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